

Acquisition of Industrial Training Skills and Its Impact on Business Education Students' Self-Efficacy in Entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to establish the relationship between acquisition of determine whether there is a relationship between acquisition of Students' Industrial Work Experience skills and Business Education Students' self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship. Three research questions guided the study and one hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted correlation design. The population of the study was 1,595 year three and year four Business Education Students in Rivers State Universty and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and the sample size was 480 Business Education Students that have undergone SIWES. Two self-structured sets of questionnaires were used for the study; the first instrument was to find out the skills acquired by Business Education students during SIWES and the second instrument was to find out the self-efficacy Level of Business Education Students toward entrepreneurship. The instruments were validated by two experts in Business Education Department and a Measurement and Evaluation expert all in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The reliability of the instruments were achieved through Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which yielded a reliability index of 0.75 for ITS BES and 0.83 for SELBES. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to establish the relationship between the two variables. T-test for correlation analysis was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant and decision was made based on the t-value. Findings from the study revealed that Business Education Students acquired communication skills, leadership skills relationship building skill, self confidence and self motivation problem solving skill and so on. It was also reveal that business education students have high self-efficacy level to entrepreneurship after SIWES training. Finally, it was reveal ($r=0.54$), indicating that a positive relationship exist between SIWES and self-efficacy. Therefore, there is significant relationship between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities. It was recommended amongst others that since SIWES increases the self-efficacy level of students, the government and the institutions should offer some form of award to students that performed excellently during the training period, as this will motivate other students to take the training period serious.

Keywords: Skills Acquisition, SIWES, Self-efficacy and Entrepreneurship

INTRODUCTION

In this 21st century skills acquisition is obviously becoming more tectonic than just earning a degree in any professional and one-way higher institutions exposes their students to the process of skills acquisition is through Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES). SIWES was introduced in 1973 by Industrial Training Fund to Nigerian higher institutions. Students' industrial work experience scheme is a skill acquisition training scheme organized by Industrial Training Funds (ITF) which is supported by tertiary institutions and organisations in Nigeria. (Olaoye, Mathe, Ojebiyi, & Nwekoyo, 2017). This is a practical training aimed at bridging the gap between the theory and practical (Chen tyowuah & Akor, 2019). SIWES according to Anyaeneh and Ochuba (2019), is a skill development scheme that was designed to expose and prepare students for the industrial work situation in order to achieve technical and entrepreneurial skills through various firms, industries and factories. They also noted that before the introduction of the scheme there was a growing concern among Nigerian industrialists that the graduates the institutions produce lacked adequate practical skills or experiences needed for employment. It was on this basis that SIWES was introduced to provide students with the opportunity of exposure to enable them acquire prerequisite practical knowledge and skills.

Business Education students are expected to undergo SIWES in other to acquire practical business skills. The Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), also called Industrial Training is a compulsory skills training programme designed to expose and prepare students of Nigerian Universities to acquire real business skills (Onyemauwa, 2020).). Business Education students upon the completion of their year two courses are required to go for SIWES training for a period of six months (6 months). SIWES is a planned and structured programme and it is based on stated and specific career objectives which are directed toward the development of occupational competencies of students. SIWES is being powered by the Federal Government of Nigeria and Industrial Training Fund (ITF). SIWES equip students with practical experiences through experiential learning and the educational experience of the learner is expected to cover the intellectual, social, emotional, physical, and spiritual growth of the learner and not just academic growth (Morgan 2017; Schiro, 2013). Experiential

learning involves a hands-on approach to learning. It makes learning an experience that moves beyond the classroom and strives to bring in a more involved way of learning (Wikipedia, 2021). SIWES as a programme enables Business Education students to be exposed to practical knowledge and acquire skills that enhance them to stand the test of time. The institution of higher learning also benefit from SIWES as they use the opportunity to send their students out to the industries to acquire practical skills/ experiences they cannot offer them in the classroom. Emetarom (2011) agreed to this fact that when students are exposed to SIWES it provide the institutions the opportunity to marry training to the needs of industry as well as enhancing the development of the nation and improving the occupational competencies of the participating students by equipping them with relevant skills and knowledge needed to be self-reliant and self employed.

The general skills students acquire during SIWES has been identified by Agwunan in Anyaeneh and Ochuba (2019) as teams work, presentation skill and problem-solving skills, communication and time management, improved self-confidence and self-motivation; flexibility and willingness to handle a wide range of tasks, ability to handle change, continual learning and entrepreneurial attitude, computing skills and knowledge of current information systems, and information delivery mechanisms etc. A study conducted by Olumese and Ediagbonya (2016) on Business Education Students' Evaluation of the Benefits and Challenges Confronting Student Industrial Works Experience Scheme in Edo and Delta States proves that Business Education students indeed benefit from SIWES. As identified by Bupo and Okiridu (2017), the following are objectives of the Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) as reported in Information Guidelines include: to provide opportunity for students to supplement the theoretical learning with practical activities in their various disciplines; to expose and prepare students for industrial work situations they are likely to meet after their graduation; to expose students to work methods and experiences in handling equipment and machinery that may not be available in their various educational institutions; to enlist and strengthen employees' involvement in the entire educational process of preparing students for employment in industry; and assessing the pedigree of students available for job opportunities in the future; to prepare the students for a business career by merging their analytical power with self-reliance thereby bridging the gap between theory and practice as well as making transition from school to work easier. Here the learners go out of the normal classroom to acquire business skills that will enhance what they have learnt in the classroom, going out the classroom to work in the real-business-world may increase the students' self-efficacy level.

Self-efficacy has been identified as the best factor to determine an individual's entrepreneurial mindset over the years. Gaumer- Erickson & Noonan (2018) noted that self-efficacy is a student's perception of his capabilities to achieve a specific objective, perform at a certain level, and complete moderately challenging tasks. The student's personal beliefs in his or her ability enable him or her to carry out entrepreneurial behaviour (Doanha & Bernatb, 2019). This means that the students' level of self-efficacy might determine whether he or she will have entrepreneurial mindset. As posited by Hisrich, Peter, and Shepherd (2017) entrepreneurial self-efficacy describes self confidence that leads to the behaviour of someone who can successfully carry out entrepreneurial process. When business students are able to acquire the necessary business skills, it might develop their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship. Different scholars have defined entrepreneurial self-efficacy from perspectives. Some researchers have defined it as entrepreneurs' self-confidence in term of performing a specific task while others have described entrepreneurial self-efficacy as an individual's confidence in his or her ability to accomplish the entrepreneurial process. (Doanha & Bernatb, 2019). Self-efficacy is a person's confidence in their own ability to perform a specific task. Self-efficacy influences the motivation and ability to engage in a particular activity (Bandura in Barakats, Boddington, & Vyarkarnam, 2014).

According to Campo (2011), individuals with a high level of self-efficacy have a higher chance of venturing into entrepreneurship, as a person who has high self-efficacy level for a particular task tend to engage in it and then is ready to persevere in that task compared to an individual who shows low level of self-efficacy. Therefore, an individual' entrepreneurial self-efficacy can influence his or her intention toward entrepreneurship. Li and Wu (2019) stated that self-efficacy encourages one to persevere in most of the setbacks and challenges encountered in the entrepreneurial process. Campo (2011) viewed self-efficacy as the level of an individual's confidence in starting a new business. Doanha and Bernatb (2019) noted that from the entrepreneurial standpoint Self-efficacy has been defined as an individual's belief in their capability to complete a task Bandura (2012) posited that self-efficacy is the most influential factor that affects human behaviour because it influences behaviour both directly and indirectly as a result of its impact on other processes. Trevelyan (2011) stated that Previous research has shown that entrepreneurial self-efficacy highly affects individual' intention and competence to become an entrepreneur, the amount of effort they need to devote in create a new business, challenges of a new venture creation process, the persistence they will need to face the changes and their success in performing entrepreneurial action and tasks. Chen in Lope Pihie and Bagheri (2013) posits that those students with a strong sense of self- efficacy will successfully perform entrepreneurial

tasks such as marketing, financial control, management and risk taking have higher intentions to become entrepreneurs than those with low beliefs in their entrepreneurial abilities and skills.

Statement of the Problem

The Students' Industrial Work Experience scheme is designed to expose students in higher institutions to the industrial world, in order for them to acquire practical skills in their different fields of study. The government and other key players introduced this programme to bridge the gap between theory and practice and to prepare the students to be employable and to become entrepreneurs.

But, for decades now, students of higher institutions past through SIWES and entrepreneurship courses, yet, after graduation some of them prefer to search for white-collar jobs. And it is so oblivious that every year the higher institutions graduate students into the labour market without adequate and corresponding job opportunities out there and Business Education Students are not excluded from this unfortunate situation. As affirmed by Efido and Ogbu (2020), some graduates depend on white-collar jobs which are not forthcoming. Few graduates are willing to become self-employed because they perceived the business creation process as cumbersome. This has led to increased unemployment, crimes and other social vices, affecting both the graduates and the society. And from the researcher's observation, few researches have been done on this aspect to determine whether there is a relationship between acquisition of Students' Industrial Work Experience skills and Business Education Students' self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship.

On this note, the researcher sought to know the relationship between acquisition of Students Industrial Work Experience Skills and Business Education Students' self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities?

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between the skills acquired by business education students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES.
2. Determine the self-efficacy level of Business Education Students toward entrepreneurship
3. Determine the relationship between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES?
2. What is the self-efficacy level of Business Education Students toward entrepreneurship?
3. What is the relationship between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlation research design, to establish the relationship between SIWES and self-efficacy. The study was carried out in Rivers State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 1,595 year three and year four Business Education Students in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University Education and the sample size was 480 Business Education Students that have undergone SIWES. The researcher adopted Purposive sampling technique for the study because the members of the population have the desired characteristics and knowledge of the subject matter. Two self-structured sets of questionnaires were used for the study; the first instrument was to find out the skills acquired by Business Education students during SIWES and the second instrument was to find out the self-efficacy Level of Business Education Students toward entrepreneurship. The instruments were structured on a 4 point rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA 4points), Agreed (A 3 Points), Disagreed/ (D 2 Points), and Strongly Disagreed (SD1point) for instrument 1 and High Level (HL 4points), Moderate Level (ML 3 Points), Low Level (LL 2 Points) and Very Low Level (VLL 1point) for instrument 2. The instruments were validated by two experts in Business Education Department and

a Measurement and Evaluation expert all in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The reliability of the instruments were achieved through Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which yielded a reliability index Of 0.75 for ITSBES and 0.83 for SELBES. The instruments were administered personally by the researcher with the aid of a research assistant. A total of 480 questionnaires were distributed and 420 copies were retrieved. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to establish the relationship between the two variables. T-test for correlation analysis was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant and decision was made based on the t-value.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES?

Table 1: Respondent rating of the Mean and Standard Deviation of the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES

		N=420						
s/n	Item	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	std Deviati on	Remarks
1	I learnt how to communicate better during my SIWES	259	144	6	11	3.55	0.66	Agreed
2	I was exposed to official presentation during my SIWES	124	266	30	0	3.22	0.56	Agreed
3	I undertook Leadership roles during my SIWES	235	96	76	13	3.32	0.88	Agreed
4	My SIWES period taught me how to build proper relationship.	92	245	81	2	3.02	0.66	Agreed
5	I developed human relation skills during my SIWES.	222	128	70	0	3.36	0.75	Agreed
6	I was tasked with assignment that made me to use my initiative during my SIWES	114	194	112	0	3.00	0.73	Agreed
7	I learnt how to be creative and innovative during my SIWES	179	154	73	0	3.39	0.99	Agreed
8	I developed problem solving skills during my SIWES	136	173	78	31	3.01	0.94	Agreed
9	My SIWES period built my self confidence and Self motivation	217	163	9	31	3.35	0.85	Agreed
10	During my SIWES period I was able to work independently	159	156	44	61	2.99	1.03	Agreed
11	My SIWES period enabled me to develop social interaction skills	176	187	18	39	3.19	0.89	Agreed
12	I was able to handle equipment and machinery during my SIWES	136	195	72	17	3.07	0.81	Agreed
13	I worked in a team during my SIWES	130	228	46	16	3.12	0.75	Agreed
14	I developed ability to handle change during my SIWES	177	176	47	20	3.21	0.82	Agreed
15	I developed the ability to take every task serious during my SIWES	130	149	96	45	2.87	0.98	Agreed
16	I developed Managerial skills during my SIWES	163	166	54	37	3.08	0.93	Agreed
17	During my SIWES period I was able to identify and exploit new business opportunities	130	163	124	3	3,00	0.80	Agreed
18	My SIWES period taught me how to undertake	149	199	42	30	3.11	0.85	agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The analysis in table 1 shows that the students of Business Education acquired the following skills during their SIWES period; communication skills (M=3.55, SD=0.66) followed by leadership skill (M=3.32,SD=0.88),

relationship building skill (M=3.36, SD=0.75), self confidence and self motivation (M=3.35, SD=0.85), ability to hand change (M=3.21,SD=0.82), social interaction skills (M=3.19, SD=0.89), teamwork (M=3.12,SD=0.75) and ability to undertake risk (M=3.11, SD=0.85).

Research Question 2: What is the self-efficacy Level of Business Education Students toward entrepreneurship after SIWES?

Table 2: Respondent rating of the Mean and Standard Deviation of the self-efficacy level of Business Education Students toward entrepreneurship after SIWES

s/n	Item	HL	ML	L	VL	\bar{X}	std Deviation	Remarks
1	I am able to achieve most of my entrepreneurial goals that I have set for myself.	247	76	74	23	3.30	0.95	High level
2	When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.	150	156	110	4	3.08	0.81	High level
3	I can obtain entrepreneurship outcomes that are important to me.	115	212	93	0	3.05	0.70	High level
4	I can succeed at almost any business I set my mind.	183	143	94	0	3.21	0.78	High level
5	I am able to successfully overcome many challenges in business creation.	207	174	39	0	3.40	0.65	High level
6	I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.	249	128	34	9	3.47	0.74	High level
7	Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well.	173	125	107	15	3.09	0.90	High level
8	I avoid challenging tasks.	145	118	75	69	2.90	1.14	High level
9	I think that difficult tasks or situations are beyond my Control or capability.	113	149	96	60	2.76	1.02	High level
10	I focus on negative outcomes or personal failures more	147	82	122	69	2.73	1.11	High level
11	I am unable to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself.	115	150	86	69	2.74	1.03	High level
12	I don't think I can succeed at any endeavour to which I set my mind.	142	93	115	70	2.73	1.10	High level
13	I am not confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.	119	132	108	61	2.74	1.03	High level
14	Compared to other people, I cannot do most tasks very well.	141	110	54	115	2.66	1.20	High level
	Grand mean					2.99	0.94	High level

The result from Table 2 shows Business Education Student's Self-Efficacy level is high, with a grand mean of (2.99, SD=0.94), indicating high Self-Efficacy level. This results shows that the students strongly indicated that they have the confidence to perform effectively on many different tasks (M=3.47, SD=0.74) followed by ability to overcome many challenges (M=3.40, SD=0.65), achieve most of the entrepreneurial goals they set for themselves (M=3.30, SD=0.95), ability to succeed in any business they set their mind (M=3.21, SD=0.78), compared to others, they can do most tasks very well (M=3.09, SD=0.90), when faced with difficult tasks they can accomplish them (M=3.08, SD=0.81) and obtain outcomes that are important to them (M=3.05, SD=0.70).

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities?

Table 3: The relationship between SIWES and the Self-Efficacy Level of Business Education Students

Variables	ΣX	ΣY	ΣXY	r	Remark
SIWES	1,326.78		1,666,157.16	0.54	Positive
Self-efficacy level		1,255.79			

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The analysis from table 3 showed ($r=0.54$), indicating that a positive relationship exist between SIWES and self-efficacy. This means that increase in SIWES training will lead to increase in self-efficacy level of Business Education Students toward entrepreneurship.

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant relationship between the learning experiences acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities

Table 3.1: t-test result for test of the significant relationship between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES training and their self-efficacy level Toward Entrepreneurship

Variable	ΣX	ΣY	ΣXY	t_{rxy}	t-crit	P	level sig.	df	decision
SIWES	1,326.78								
			1,666,157.16	8.44	1.96	0.00	0.05	419	Rejected
Self-efficacy level		1,255.79							

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The analysis in table 3 showed that the t-calculated is greater than t-critical ($t_{cal} > t_{crit}$). Hence, the hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is significant relationship between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level toward entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities.

Discussion of Findings

It was found that Business Education Students were able to communication better during SIWES period, they took up leadership roles, were able to build proper relationship, the SIWES period enable the students to develop self confidence and self motivation, ability to hand change, social interaction skills, the students had the opportunity to work in a team the students have the ability to undertake risk, they developed problem solving skills during SIWES, they were able to work independently during the SIWES period, the students had the opportunity to handle equipment and machinery during my SIWES, they developed the ability to take every task serious during SIWES and developed Managerial skills during SIWES .

This finding is in agreement with the view of Mgaya and Mbekomize (2014) that when student participate in SIWES they gain skills such as communication, presentation, leadership, relationship building, , human relations, team-work, , initiative, time management, enterprise, abilities to solve problems and persuade. Also, it is in agreement Karunaratne and Perera (2018), study on students' perceptions on the positive learning experiences as regards to internship. It was found that during internship the students had the chance to aspire for future education and career, execute problem solving activities, develop self-confidence, and develop social interaction skill. Finally, Bukaliya and Mashonaland (2012) opined that Internship provides an opportunity for interns to obtain a first-hand experience in the real working environment and this will build their confidence.

It was found that Business Education Students have high Self Efficacy Level after the experiential learning period, as they were able to; develop their confident to perform effectively on many different tasks, they had the ability to overcome many challenges, achieve most of the goals they set for themselves, they had the ability to succeed in any endeavour they set their mind compared to others, they can do most tasks very well, when faced with difficult tasks they can accomplish them and they obtain outcomes that are important to them.

This finding is in agreement with the findings of Othman and Hisam (2020), that students who learnt entrepreneurship education courses in polytechnic institutions in Malaysia show a slightly higher level of entrepreneurial self-efficacy compared to students who have never been exposed to entrepreneurial knowledge, especially in the aspects of generating business ideas, business planning, building business networks, and managing human resources. Also, Campo (2011) noted that individuals with a high level of self-efficacy have a higher chance of venturing into entrepreneurship, as a person who has high self-efficacy level for a particular task tend to engage in it and then is ready to persevere in that task compared to an individual who shows low level of self-efficacy.

There is a positive relationship existing between learning experiences acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self efficacy level o. It is clear from this point that, increase in SIWES will lead to increase in self-efficacy when the self-efficacy level of the students increases toward entrepreneurship, they can easily take up entrepreneurial actions. As there is significant relationship between the learning experiences acquired by Business Education Students during internship (SIWES) and their self-efficacy level in Rivers State Universities. This finding is in line with the finding of Sunyoto, Nugroho and Ulum (2017) that there is a positive correlation between internship and entrepreneurship interest.

Also, it was found that a positive relationship exists between the skills acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES level indicating that increase in (SIWES) will lead to increase in perceived desirability level of the students. When the self-efficacy level of the students increases toward entrepreneurship, they can easily take up entrepreneurial actions, as there is significant relationship between the learning experiences acquired by Business Education Students during SIWES and their self-efficacy level in Rivers State Universities.

CONCLUSION

Student industrial experience scheme bridges the gap between the classroom and the industrial/business world. The students are privileged to leave the regular classroom to the real business environment to work as casual staff for a space of six (6) months. This builds their self confidence as business students, they are motivated as they faced the real business world and they can easily take up entrepreneurial activity after the training.

In this present 21st century and Nigerian economy, the universities should strive to prepare their students to face the economic realities, the way to overcome this, is through skills acquisition.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

1. The Industrial Training Fund and the various Institutions responsible for sending students out for SIWES should ensure that the students are attached to the appropriate organisations that will equip the students with relevant skills based on students' departments and course of study. Also, the programme should be supervised closely, to ensure that each student participates in the training programme. The only way students can acquire the desired skills from SIWES is by participate in the training process.
2. Since SIWES increases the self-efficacy level of students that participate in the training, the students should be advised to get the best of out the training.
3. The relationship that exists between SIWES and self-efficacy is a positive one; therefore, the government and institutions should offer some form of award to students that performed excellently during the training period, as this will motivate other students to take the training period serious.

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